

established by comparison with an authentic specimen (m.p., m.m.p., superimposable ir).

The residue from benzene : CHCl_3 (9 : 1) eluates afforded betulin crystallises from benzene-methanol (18 mg), m.p. 253-255°; acetate m.p. 220-223°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +21^\circ$ (c 0.30 in CHCl_3). The latter was identical with authentic betulin acetate¹¹ (m.p., m.m.p., ir).

The leaves of *W. fruticosa* was thus found to contain lupeol (0.023%), β -sitosterol (0.008%), betulin (0.004%), ursolic acid (0.022%), betulinic acid (0.001%) and minute quantity of oleanolic acid.

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Chemical Investigation of *Viscum articulatum*

SARMILA RAY, T. N. THAKUR,** AMITABHA GHOSH
and

A. K. BARUA*

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Calcutta-700 009

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VISCUM articulatum (Loranthaceae) is an epiphyte. No work on the chemical constituents of the plant appears to have been reported in the literature. We now report the result of chemical investigation on this plant.

The plant growing on *Diospyros peregrina* was collected from the district of Hazaribagh, Bihar.

** St. Columbus College, Hazaribagh.

Three neutral and two acid triterpenes were isolated from the benzene extract of the air-dried and crushed plant material.

The neutral triterpenes were isolated in pure state from the mixture by repeated tlc over silica gel G impregnated with AgNO_3 following the reported method¹. The triterpenes thus obtained had melting points 186°, 211-212° and 258°, respectively. The compound having m.p. 186° has molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+426); monoacetate, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ (M^+468), m.p. 225°. Its mass spectral peaks at m/e 189, 207 and 218 were very similar to those of α -amyrin. The compound was identified as α -amyrin by comparing its m.p., m.m.p., tlc and glc data with an authentic sample. The compound having m.p. 211-212° has molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+426); monoacetate, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ (M^+468), m.p. 213-215°. The compound was identified as lupeol by comparison of its m.p., tlc and glc data with an authentic sample. The compound having m.p. 258° has molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ (M^+442). Its mass spectral peaks at m/e 189, 203, 207, 220 and 234 were very similar to those of betulin². The compound was identified as betulin by comparing its m.p., m.m.p., tlc and glc data with an authentic sample.

The two acid triterpenes could be isolated from the mixture by repeated tlc over silica gel G (solvent, CHCl_3 : petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) : $\text{HOAc} = 64 : 33 : 3$ v/v]. The acids thus obtained had m.p. 304-308° and 314-316°, respectively. The acid, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_3$, having m.p. 304-308° formed a monomethyl ester, $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_3$ (M^+470), m.p. 199-200°, on treatment with ethereal diazomethane. The mass spectrum of the ester showed characteristic peaks at m/e 207 and 262. The acid was identified as oleanolic acid by direct comparison of its m.p., m.m.p., tlc and glc data of its methyl ester with an authentic sample of methyl oleanolate. The second acid, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_3$, m.p. 314-316°, formed a monomethyl ester, $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_3$, m.p. 224-225° (M^+470). The mass spectrum of the methyl ester showed peaks at m/e 189, 202, 203, 207, 220 and 262, very similar to those of methyl betulinate³ and was also supported by the nmr spectrum of the methyl ester. Finally, the acid was identified as betulinic acid by comparison of m.p., m.m.p., tlc and glc data of the methyl ester with an authentic sample.

It should be pointed out that mixture of α -amyrin, lupeol and betulin and also oleanolic acid, ursolic acid and betulinic acid are of common occurrence in the plant kingdom. Separation of individual constituents from above type of mixture even by preparative tlc is difficult and time-consuming. This can, however, be easily achieved by glc as described below.

Glc of some triterpenes: The instrument used was a Pye Unicam, model GCD gas chromatograph equipped with columns (1.8 m x 3 mm i.d.) containing 3% and 6% SE-30; carrier gas N_2 at 60 ml min^{-1} ; column temp. 260° and 312°; detection and injection temp. 300° and 350°, respectively).

Derivatisation : About 1 mg each of the samples were dissolved in 10 μ l of dried and distilled pyridine and to each 10 μ l of *N,O*-bis(trimethylsilyl)acetamide⁸ (Pierce Chemical, U.S.A.) was added and kept at 80° for 15 min. The sample (1-2 μ l) was injected into the gas chromatograph. The retention time of the various compounds have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compounds	Retention times (minutes)
α -Amyrin	8.4
Lupeol	9.6
Betulin	18.6
Methyl betulinate	11.6
Methyl oleanolate	19.4
Methyl ursolate	19.8

Acetyl derivatives of the methyl esters of oleanolic, betulinic and ursolic acids were also gas chromatographed on the same column. The retention times were found longer than those of the trimethylsilyl ethers. Moreover, there were considerable trailing of the peaks and no separation was observed in the case of betulinic and oleanolic acids.

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Chemical Examination of *Pterocarpus marsupium*

JAMES MATHEW and A. V. SUBBA RAO

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

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The powdered heartwood of *Pterocarpus marsupium* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform. The petroleum ether extract on chromatography (Si-gel, eluent chloroform) yielded a colourless compound (0.01%), m.p. 294°, [α]_D +74° (c 0.95 in CHCl₃) which was characterised as oleanolic acid [lit.¹ m.p. 310°, [α]_D +78° (CHCl₃)] the identity of which was confirmed with mixed m.p. and superimposable ir spectrum with an authentic sample. This is the first instance of oleanolic acid from a *Pterocarpus* species, eventhough

closely related acetyloleanolic acid has been found⁹ to be present in these woods.

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2a : R=H
2b : R=Me
2c : R=Ac

3a : R=H
3b : R=Me
3c : R=Ac

The petroleum ether extract also yielded pterostilbene (1) which we have reported⁸ earlier. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of pterostilbene (1) has now been recorded ; that of stilbenes appears to be scanty as reported in literature. The ¹³C {¹H} nmr spectrum (90 MHz ; DMSO-d₆) of compound 1 showed 10 signals corresponding to the 16 carbon atoms of its molecular formula. The multiplicities in the off-resonance spectrum were in agreement with the assignments. The spectrum showed signals at δ 128.28 (s, C-1'), 127.65 (d, C-2', 6'), 115.30 (d, C-3', 5') and 160.38 (s, C-4') assignable to the carbon atoms of the ring B, approximately comparable to the signals due to the corresponding carbons of *p*-cresol⁶ ; δ 157.13 (s, C-3, 5), 103.81 (d, C-2, 6), 98.99 (d, C-4) (the lone carbon appearing upfield by virtue of its *ortho*-relation to two oxygen functions on the aromatic rings) and 54.83 (OMe). Only one signal at δ 124.89 (d) was available to be assigned to both C- α and C- β . A signal at δ 139.35 (s) was tentatively assigned to C-1.

The chloroform extract on chromatography (Si-gel, eluent : chloroform-ethylacetate) gave compounds 2a and 3a. Compound 2a (0.012%), yellow prisms, crystallised from ethylacetate-chloroform, m.p. 200° ; C₁₅H₁₂O₄, M⁺ 256 ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1640 cm⁻¹ (chelated CO) ; λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 245 (3.96), 325 sh, 370 nm (4.45) ; was identified as 4,2',4'-trihydroxychalcone as its m.p.⁸ and uv data⁹ agreed with those reported. In the ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound 2a, the signals due to the